

New species of *Euxoa* Hübner, 1821 from Asia (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), II.

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Abstract. Description of four new *Euxoa* species with 23 color illustrations, 11 genitalia figures and 3 habitat photos.

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, *Euxoa*, new species, taxonomy, Asia.

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Introduction

The first part of the results of the author's studies on the genus *Euxoa* was published in the Entomofauna (Gyulai, 2018), with the description of seven new species (*Euxoa exclaviota* sp.n., *Euxoa nesopatris* sp.n., *Euxoa pseudolugens* sp.n., *Euxoa transoxanica* sp.n., *Euxoa subcognita* sp.n., *Euxoa transiliensis* sp.n., *Euxoa stenomelas* sp.n.) and one new subspecies (*Euxoa dsheiron syriae* ssp.n.). In the first part, the author reviewed the short history of research on the extremely diverse, mostly with Holarctic distribution pattern, *Euxoa* genus and revealed the most important publications up to that point. The majority of the *Euxoa* species being confined to Asia have a wide range of distribution, but there are also extremely local and rare species, of which only the holotype or a few specimens have become known even in the last 150 years. Although the Asian *Euxoa* fauna is now well known, during the intensive research of the last few years some further new species have been found, mostly one or a few specimens. This fact resulted, in some of the new descriptions being provided below, based on a single specimen. Both the male and female genitalia of *Euxoa* display remarkable resemblance and the genitalia configuration is hardly distinctive even in the species being very distinctive in the external characters. Therefore, implementing the descriptions needed careful genitalia study, particularly when only one of the sexes was found in the author's and in the largest private and museum collections. The recent publication is an addition to the knowledge of the *Euxoa* fauna of Asia with the description of the following four new taxa: *Euxoa akzharae* sp. n., *Euxoa subhissarica* sp. n., *Euxoa kopetbina* sp. n., and *Euxoa pseudoladakhensis* sp. n.

The new taxa and closely related species are illustrated with imagines in colour and male and female genitalia.

All the figured specimens in colour are deposited in the collection of P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein: GYP = genitalia slide of Péter Gyulai; PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); VZ = genitalia slide of Zoltán Varga; m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype; prov. = province.

Material. The article is based on the private collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary), however, type material documentation was preserved by Zoltán Varga (University of Debrecen, Hungary) as well.

Description of the new species.

Euxoa akzharae sp. n. (Figs 1, 33)

Holotype. Female, S Kazakhstan, Kyzylorda reg. Jalagash Distr, 7 km E of Akzhar vill., 45.0572 N, 64.1674 E 100 m, 23. IX. 2022, leg. V. Zurlina, slide no. GYP 5902 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Diagnosis. *E. akzharae* sp. n. (Fig. 1) belongs to the most unmistakable *Euxoa* species. The only very similar species is *Euxoa transoxanica* Gyulai, 2018 (Fig. 2). The main distinctive external differential character is the almost clear white hindwing with fine, blackish, interrupted terminal line in the medial section of the costal edge and the clear white cilia of *E. akzharae* sp. n.; while in *E. transoxanica* the hindwing whitish in the basal field, then more and more intensively brown suffused, conspicuously in the broad, dark brown suffused marginal area without the fine, blackish, interrupted terminal line in the medial section in the costal edge; the cilia pale brownish. Further external differential features are the unicolorous, pale fawn-coloured fore-wing in the new species, while it is pale brown or pale ochreous shaded in the females of *E. transoxanica* (only among the males are pale fawn-coloured or with whitish forewing specimens). The new species has a slight greyish trace in the place of the reniform stigma and fine blackish interrupted terminal line, and a slight trace of the end of the antemedial and postmedial transverse lines; while the forewing of most of the *E. transoxanica* specimens is without wing pattern, but sparsely dispersed by pale brown scales; or – in certain specimens of the slightly darker females – with very faint, light brownish traces of the end of the antemedial and postmedial transverse lines and the reniform stigmata. The fine blackish and interrupted terminal line is present on the forewing of *E. akzharae* sp. n., however absent of all the specimens of the type series of *E. transoxanica*.

The female genitalia of *E. akzharae* sp. n. (Fig. 33) can be easily distinguished from *E. transoxanica* (Fig. 34) by the longer ovipositor and the angular and shovel-like laminar plate of the antrum.

Description. Wingspan 39 mm. An easily recognizable species; antennae of female fine, filiform. The head and thorax vesture, the forewing ground colour, and its cilia unicolorous, pale fawn-coloured. The forewing almost without wing pattern, with few sparsely dispersed pale brown scales; the only discernible patterns were the slight greyish trace in the place of the reniform stigma, the fine, blackish, interrupted terminal line, and the faint, obsolescent trace of the end of the antemedial and postmedial transverse lines, being the same colour as the ground colour, but slightly darker. The hind wing clear white, slightly with diffuse pale brown suffusion in the marginal area; the discal spot not discernible. The hindwing is bordered with fine, blackish, interrupted terminal line in the medial costal edge; fringe white. The underside of the wings white-whitish.

In the female genitalia (Fig. 33) the ovipositor elongated, terminally rounded, apophyses anteriores medium long, strong, apophyses posteriores very long, finer, about twice as long as apophyses anteriores. The laminar plate of the antrum very individual in *Euxoa*, angular and shovel-like. Ductus bursae membranous, tubular, and long, the laminar plates on its wall long, with the same length, distally broadening. Appendix bursae somewhat postero-laterally positioned, broadly conical, prominent, corpus bursae large, saccate. The male is unknown.

Distribution. The new species is known only from the type locality.

Etymology. The new species is named by its halophile ecology and the similar colouration of its wings to its habitat. *Akzhar* (Kazakh: Ақжар; Russian: Акжар) is a salt lake group in the Zhambyl and Turkistan regions, near *Akzhar* in Kazakhstan.

Euxoa subhissarica sp. n. (Figs 4, 24)

Holotype. Male, Kyrgyz Republic, Naryn Region, Kochkor District, Dolon Pass, 41.8785 N, 75.7055 E, 2700 m, 27. IX. 2022, leg. V. Zurlina, slide no. GYP 5903 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Diagnosis. The new species (Fig. 4) is the Kyrgyz sister species of *Euxoa hissarica* Varga, 1990 (Figs 3, 5) which occurs in Afghanistan and the Hissar Mts. in Tajikistan. *E. subhissarica*

sp. n. is much smaller than *E. hissarica*; its wingspan 31 mm while 34-37 mm of the close relative species. The new species has less elongate forewing apex, the antemedial line is less oblique, and there is a prominence in the fore section of the postmedial line while the further section is much oblique. The ground colour of the forewing is much lighter, rather pale ochre-red-brown. The hindwing is also much lighter, and whitish, with scattered pale brown scales, particularly in the diffuse marginal area. The very different flight period also can be indicative of the correct species identity; the male of the new species was found only at the end of September, while all the studied *E. hissarica* specimens in the larger collections, known from the summer period in July and August.

Description. The wingspan 31 mm. Antennae filiform. Head and thorax pale red brown. Forewing ground colour and cilia mono-chromatic pale ochre-red-brown, from the wing pattern only the brown antemedial and postmedial transverse lines sharply defined, while the orbicular and reniform stigmata absent. The antemedial line tortuous, interrupted and slightly oblique. The postmedial line arched, and lacy, with a prominence in the fore section, then somewhat oblique toward the inner edge of the forewing. The terminal line fine, brown, and interrupted. The hindwing whitish, with scattered pale brownish scales, particularly in the margin. The wing pattern absent, cilia pale reddish. The underside of the wings whitish, with only the diffuse shade of the postmedial line in the forewing and the medial line of the hindwing visible.

The male genitalia (Fig. 24) can be characterized by the strong and apically pointed uncus, terminated with a few small bristles; the subquadrangular juxta, dorsally-medially with v-shaped incision and with triangular ventral extension; the strongly convex dorsal edge of the elongate and broad valvae with dorsally elongated cucullus section, terminated a row of strong setae. The most remarkable further features the arched, fine and long harpe and the strongly asymmetrical saccular processes, from which the right one significantly longer, and almost reaches the ventral end of the setae of the cucullus; vinculum v-shaped. The aedeagus strong, curved ventrad. The vesica tube recurved dorsad, medially with a broad, elongated slightly granulated field. The ventral subbasal diverticulum large, prominent, and globular; the medial one not prominent, and elongate-flattened. The female is unknown.

Distribution. The new species is known only from the type locality.

Etymology. The new species is named by the similarity to its closest relative species.

***Euxoa kopetbina* sp. n.** (Figs 6, 26)

Holotype. Male, Iran, prov. Khorasan, Kopet Dagh Mts., 80 km NE of Quchan, 14–15. VII. 2000, leg. B. Benedek, slide no. GYP 5794 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary).

Diagnosis. *Euxoa kopetbina* sp. n. (Fig. 6) is the sister taxa of *Euxoa aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941 (Fig. 8) (the eastern subspecies of *Euxoa aneucta* Brandt, 1938 (Fig. 7), being a rare endemic species in the Zagros Mts., in SW Iran) which is confined to the Binaloud Mts. in NE Iran, while the new species seems to be endemic in the Kopet Dagh, another, but lower mountainous range of NE Iran. *Euxoa subeucta* Varga, 2014 (Fig. 9) is similar only in the genitalia configuration, but very different both in the external features and the distribution pattern. The separation of the two close relative taxa is very easy since *E. kopetbina* sp. n. is much smaller than *E. aneucta binaloudica*; with wingspan 26 mm and 36-38 mm, respectively. Additionally, the new species has conspicuously lighter, monochromatic pale brownish ground colour of the forewings, with hardly defined wing pattern, on which only the diffuse, pale traces of the noctuid maculation and the double antemedial line discernible; while the forewings are strictly darker, fuscous, with well defined, blackish noctuid maculation and transverse lines of the *E. aneucta binaloudica*. The hindwing considerably lighter, whitish of the new species, than that of the close relative taxa. In the male genitalia of *E. kopetbina* sp. n., (Fig. 26) the most conspicuous differences are the finer, longer uncus, the dorsally evenly tapering juxta with less deep medial incision, significantly shorter vinculum, and less asymmetric saccular extensions in the new species, than in the closest relatives (Figs 27, 28, 29).

Description. The wingspan 26 mm. Antennae filiform with very fine bipectination. Vesture of the head and thorax, the ground colour of the forewing and its fringe pale brown. The wing pattern hardly defined, only the diffuse, pale traces of the noctuid maculation and of the double

antemedial line discernible. Hindwing whitish, with very diffuse light brownish suffusion in the margin. The underside of the wings without wing pattern, the forewings unicolourous pale light brownish, and the hindwings clear white.

The male genitalia (Fig. 26) can be characterized by the evenly fine and long uncus; the subquadrangular, dorsally evenly tapering juxta, dorsally-medially with v-shaped incision and with triangular ventral extension; slightly convex dorsal margin of the elongate and broad valvae with dorsally elongate cucullus section, terminated a row of strong setae. The most characteristic further features the arched, slender and long harpe and the very slightly asymmetrical saccular processes, from which the right one slightly longer; both of them slightly overhanging the ventral end of the setae of the cucullus; vinculum v-shaped. The aedeagus strong, and straight, in the vesica tube the ventral subbasal diverticulum large, and globular; the medial one not prominent, elongate-flattened. The female is unknown.

Distribution. The new species is known only from the type locality.

Etymology. The name of the new species is edited from the name of the two mountains where the habitats are of the new species and the close relative taxa.

***Euxoa pseudoladakhensis* sp. n.** (Figs 10, 11, 12, 13, 30)

Holotype. Male, Pakistan, Karakoram, 2310 m, n. Chaprot, above Chalt Nagar village, 18 - 19. IX. 1998, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai, slide no. GYP 5741 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary). Paratypes. 3 males, 1 female, with the same data as of the holotype (PGM); 5 males, 11 females, Pakistan, 2800 m, Karakoram Mts., Naltar valley, 74°12'E, 36°09,6'N, 26 - 27. IX. 1998, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 male, Pakistan, 2050 m, Hindukush Mts., E of Gupis, Daalti village, 16-17. IX. 1998, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 2 males, 1 female, Pakistan, Kashmir, 2910m, Himalaya range, Deosai Mts., n. Bubin village, 74°59'E, 35°12,6'N, 21 - 22. IX. 1998, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 male, Pakistan, 3030 m, Himalaya Mts., Kaghan valley, n. Dzhekhats village, 13-14. IX. 1998, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM). slides: GYP 1810f, 1828m, 1841f, 5728f, 5739m, 5740f, 5742m.

Diagnosis. The not completely uniform individuals of *Euxoa pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. (Figs 10, 11, 12, 13) resemble the darker-coloured individuals of *Euxoa ladakhensis* Hacker, 1996 (Fig. 20), but their genitalia differs significantly so much that they are not the most related species. On the other hand, based on the male and female genitalia configuration, *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. is the close relative of *Euxoa ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881) (Figs 14, 15), although externally they are very different, except the monochromatic forms of *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Figs 16, 17). Many publications deal with the taxonomy of the Holarctic *E. ochrogaster* species complex (Lafontaine, J. D. 1987, etc.) and countless synonyms are known, as populations with the most diverse appearance in terms of size, colour, and pattern live in its huge distribution area. *Euxoa ochrogaster* (Guenée, 1852) is a Nearctic species, which has two Palaearctic subspecies: *E. ochrogaster islandica* (Staudinger, 1857) and *E. ochrogaster rossica*. The latter one has a wide range of distribution in Asia, with described synonyms and forms; but these do not show reliable differences in their genital markings, only unique ones are. However, the populations of the close relative *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. living in Pakistan is not only externally uniformly different from the *E. ochrogaster rossica*, but also in their genitalia. Some individuals resemble to the singlecoloured *Euxoa ladakhensis* specimens, but their genitalia differ significantly so much so that they are not closely related species. *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. conspicuously differs from *E. ochrogaster rossica* with the more or less monochromatic forewings, without the long whitish-yellowish costal field. The separation of the unicolorous coloured forms of *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. and *E. ochrogaster rossica* is possible by the obscure, but more defined forewing pattern of the new species and the different distribution patterns of the two taxa. *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. can be distinguished from *E. ladakhensis* by its darker, reddish brown, more unicolorous ground colour of the wings, while those are rather greyish suffused in the similar species and the different distribution pattern can also help in the correct identification. In the male genitalia, the most conspicuous differences between *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. (Fig. 30) and *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Fig. 31) are the longer, less asymmetric saccular extensions, of which the right one is much longer and larger,

the more prominent basal and subbasal diverticuli in the new species, than in the close relative. The male genitalia of the new species (Fig. 30) conspicuously differ from that of *E. ladakhensis* (Fig. 32) by its much higher juxta, longer saccular extension on both sides, and much larger subbasal diverticuli. In the female genitalia (Fig. 35), the most significant differences are the longer ductus bursae of the new species with much longer laminar plates on its wall, and shorter, but distally larger corpus bursae, than in *E. ladakhensis* (Fig. 37). In comparison *E. pseudoladakhensis* sp. n. (Fig. 35) and *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Fig. 36), the new species has smaller ovipositor, shorter ductus bursae, less prominent appendix bursae and slightly shorter, but more ample corpus bursae.

Description. The wingspan 34 – 37 mm. Antennae filiform of both sexes. Vesture of the head and thorax, the ground colour of the forewing and its fringe more or less unicolorous brown, reddish-brown, or pale brown on the more variegated specimens, but the marginal field always darker. The wing pattern discernible, light, or pale brownish but not sharply defined. The antemedial line zigzag, double, oblique. The postmedial line double, slightly arched, and serrate. The traces of the noctuid maculation a lighter shade of the ground colour, the orbicular and reniform stigmata very finely encircled, a darker diffuse patch visible in the reniform macule. Hindwing pale light brown, with broad, diffuse light brownish suffusion in the marginal area. The underside of the wings almost without wing pattern, the shade of the marginal fields on the forewings and hindwings unicolorous pale light brownish.

The male genitalia (Fig. 30) can be characterized by the evenly fine and long uncus; the subquadrangular, shield-like, dorsally evenly tapering juxta, dorsally-medially with deep v-shaped depression, with slight triangular ventral extension; slightly convex dorsal margin of the elongate valvae with dorsally elongate cucullus section, terminated a row of strong setae. The harpe long, slender, curved. The saccular processes very long, with the same length or very slightly asymmetrical, or the right one slightly longer; both of them reaching the ventral end of the setae of the cucullus, or the right one overhanging of it; vinculum v-shaped. The aedeagus strong, almost straight, rather short. In the vesica tube, the basal-subbasal section is ample, the ventral subbasal diverticulum large, prominent, and globular; the dorsal small one also prominent; the medial one tongue-like. In the female genitalia (Fig. 35), the ovipositor elongate, terminally rounded. Apophyses anteriores short, apophyses posteriores very long, finer, about three times as long as apophyses anteriores. The laminar plate of the antrum broadly u-shaped. Ductus bursae membranous, and tubular; the laminar plates on its wall medium long, with the same length, anteriorly acute, and distally broad. Appendix bursae somewhat posterolaterally positioned, basally broad, but not conical or prominent, corpus bursae large, saccate, and medially somewhat narrower.

Distribution. The new species is known only from the high mountains of Pakistan.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to the similarity of the variegated forms of the new species and *Euxoa ladakhensis*.

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Figures 1–8. *Euxoa* spp. and ssp. adults. **1.** *E. akzharae* **sp. n.**, HT, f, Kazakhstan, Kyzilorda, Akzhar, GYP 5902; **2.** *E. transoxanica* Gyulai, 2018, PT, f, Tajikistan, Pristanj, Dshilikulja; **3.** *E. hissarica* Varga, 1990, PT, m, Afghanistan, Badakhshan, Darrah-e-Andarab, VZ 4633; **4.** *E. subhissarica* **sp. n.**, HT, m, Kirgisia, Dolon pass, GYP 5903; **5.** *E. hissarica* Varga, 1990, m, Tajikistan, Hissar Mts., Anzob pass; **6.** *E. kopetbina* **sp. n.**, HT, m, Iran, Quchan, GYP 5794; **7.** *E. aneucta* Brandt, 1938, Iran, prov. Kerman, Kuh-e-Kabir; **8.** *E. aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941, m, Iran, Binaloud Mts., Rabieh 285.

Figures 9–16. *Euxoa* spp. and ssp. adults. **9.** *E. subeucta* Varga, 2014, PT, m, Tajikistan, W Pamir Mts.; **10.** *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, HT, m, Pakistan, Karakoram, GYP 5741; **11.** *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, PT, m, Pakistan, Hindukush, GYP 5742; **12.** *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, PT, f, Pakistan, Karakoram, GYP 5728; **13.** *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, PT, f, Pakistan, Himalaya, Deosai, GYP 5740 ; **14.** *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881), m, Mongolia, C. aimak; **15.** *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881), f, China, Qinghai; **16.** *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881), m, Tajikistan, Hissar.

Figures 17–20. *Euxoa* spp. and ssp. adults. **17.** *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881), m, China, Xinyiang, GYP 5755; **18.** *E. ladakhensis* Hacker, 1996, m, China, Tibet, Nyalam, GYP 6018; **19.** *E. ladakhensis* Hacker, 1996, f, China, Tibet, Nyalam; **20.** *E. ladakhensis* Hacker, 1996, f, China, Tibet, Nyalam, GYP 6012.

Fig. 21. One of the habitats of the type series of *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.** Pakistan, Himalaya, Deosai plateau. Expedition of P. Gyulai & A. Garai in 1998.

Fig. 22. One of the habitats of the type series of *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, Pakistan, Himalaya, Deosai Mts., near Bubin village. Expedition of P. Gyulai & A. Garai in 1998.

Fig. 23. Close to the type locality of *E. kopetbina* **sp. n.** Iran, Kopet Dagh, NE of Qucan. Expedition of P. Gyulai & A. Garai in 2006.

Figures 24–27. *Euxoa* spp. and ssp. male genitalia. **24.** *E. subhissarica* **sp. n.**, HT, Kirgisia, Dolon pass, GYP 6014; **25.** *E. hissarica* Varga, 1990, PT, Afghanistan, Badakhshan, VZ 4633; **26.** *E. kopetbina* **sp. n.**, Iran, prov. Khorasan, Kopeth Dagh Mts., GYP 5794; **27.** *E. aneucta binaloudica* Brandt, 1941, Iran, Khorasan, Binaloud Mts., Rabieh 285.

Figures 28–31. *Euxoa* spp. and ssp. male genitalia. **28.** *E. aneucta* Brandt, 1938, Iran, Zaghros, VZ 8250; **29.** *E. subeucta* Varga, 2014, PT, Tajikistan, W Pamir, GYP 1005; **30.** *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, HT, Pakistan, Karakoram, GYP 5741; **31.** *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881), Tajikistan, W Pamir, Sarez lake area, GYP 6010.

Figures 32–37. *Euxoa* spp. and ssp. male and female genitalia. **32.** *E. ladakhensis* Hacker, 1996, China, Tibet, Nyalam, GYP 6018; **33.** *E. akzharae* **sp. n.**, HT, Kazakhstan, Kyzilorda, Akzhar, GYP 5902; **34.** *E. transoxanica* Gyulai, 2018, PT, Tajikistan, Pristanj GYP4716; **35.** *E. pseudoladakhensis* **sp. n.**, PT, Pakistan, Karakoram, GYP 5728; **36.** *E. ochrogaster rossica* (Staudinger, 1881, Kyrgyzstan, Dolon pass, GYP 6014; **37.** *E. ladakhensis* Hacker, 1996, China, Tibet, Nyalam, GYP 6017.

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